

Family Upbringing and Peer Pressure as Correlates of Undergraduates' Attitude to Unrest in Universities in Southwest, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined family upbringing and peer pressure as correlates of undergraduates' attitude to unrest in Universities in Southwest, Nigeria. The descriptive research design of the survey type was used in this study. The population consisted of all undergraduates from 15 public universities in Southwest, Nigeria. The sample for this study consisted of 1,768 undergraduates selected from six public universities. The sample was selected through multistage sampling procedures. A questionnaire tagged "Undergraduates' Attitude to Unrest Questionnaire (UAUQ)" designed by the researcher was used to collect data for the study. The validity of the instrument was ensured using face and content validity. The reliability of the instrument was determined through test re-test method. A co-efficient of 0.74 was obtained from the analysis which was considered statistically high enough to make the instrument reliable. The data collected from the questionnaires were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the study revealed that students are always happy during unrest, they pay much attention and show interest in unrest, they participate actively in unrest and also prefer violence than negotiation. In addition, family upbringing and peer pressure are related to undergraduates' attitude to unrest. It was recommended among others that parents are of central significance in their children's life, so they should adequately give their children proper home training and necessary support that will be needed by the

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children in the University and throughout life.

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Introduction

The significance of university education to the national growth cannot be overstressed. However, no significant development can take place in a crisis-ridden system as seen in the educational institutions in the country recently. It seems that students' crisis is as old as the universities in Nigeria itself. Presently, students' militancy in the nation's universities has come to be an issue of serious concern. Actions such as rebellions, protests, unrests and fierceness, resulting into continuous shutting of schools for months have become a consistent characteristic of Nigerian universities.

The level at which students in universities participate in violent protests against the management of institutions or government is becoming bothersome to many stakeholders, especially parents, who professed universities as a solution to the unproductive education system in Nigeria (Ajibade, 2013). Additionally, the increase in intensity of the menace and the way it spreads from one institution to other institutions three years ago could be considered as a bad sign to the challenged education system in Nigeria.

Adeyemi, Ekundayo and Alonge (2010) described students' turbulence as a situation of tension or people intending to riot against social ills or irregularities in an organization. Students' turbulence can therefore be seen as the riots and rampages by students to show complaints or press demands to school authorities. It is the state of conflict that brings about changes in doing things, desire or tendencies. It occurs when there is a pressure or when people intend to rebel against certain social ills or irregularities in an organization. Thus, university students tend to show annoyance through anxieties, protest, demonstrations and bonfire. Strife tends to be the result of conflict which is termed as a natural and unavoidable part of people working together. On this note, Ogunlade (2005) considered unrest into two types, namely, the generalized crisis and the individualized crisis. She claimed that individualized crisis includes one person only and it could be self-inflicted while generalized crisis involves two or more people having disagreement in all its ramifications on issues of common interest.

The researcher detected that over the years the general performance of graduates in Nigerian universities and Southwest in precise appears to have been on the deterioration. Employers of labour most times do not consider some of them employable. They tend to refer to them as 'half baked' graduates because they have to go through series of training and teaching to be able to achieve up to standard. This trend appears to continue to pose a lot of challenges to these institutions of higher learning as their ability continues to be questioned. It seems that the above situation results from several factors among which appear to be students' unrest and its attendant problems.

It seems students' unrest has disturbed stability and smooth running of management in most of the universities. Students' unrest, leading to collapse of law and order, shutting of schools, expulsion of students from schools and ruin of lives and property, among others, seems to have been a major issue of serious concern to school authorities, parents, government and even students themselves. Students who could have been more valuable to themselves, the parents and the nation seem to be falling out or die during the crises thereby leading to waste of human resources.

Ige and Olowolabi (2010) defined an attitude as a mental or neural state of readiness, structured through experience, exerting a directive or dynamic influence on the individual's response to all substances and situations to which it is related. A simpler definition of attitude is a mind-set or a tendency to act in a specific way due to both an individual's experience and temperament. Typically, when we refer to a person's attitudes, we are trying to clarify his or

her behaviour. Attitudes are a complex combination of things we tend to call personality, beliefs, values, behaviours, and motivations.

A critical link in developing the measurement of attitudes toward unrest as a social pointer is to create the relationships between such attitudes and fierce behaviours. These relationships are difficult. It is part of the human situation for students to do things which are opposing to their beliefs, and it is also factual that students sometimes fail to act in accordance with their views. Nonetheless, such permutations of what might be expected are seen as deviations, and it seems reasonable to suppose that on every student are more likely to act in accordance with their beliefs than in opposition to them.

Family nurture appears to determine students' attitude towards unrest. The way parents apply the methods of effective discipline and observing will go a long way to determine students' attitude towards unrest. Marriages where there is strong bonding amid husband and wife will usually yield peaceful homes and conforming children (Carlson, 2010). The attitude of the partners towards one another will scheme images of care, trust, friendship, love/affection, respect and homeliness. This will be stimulated in their children the want for these traits and the desire to be a part of the parents' bonding. Parents who live peacefully will more easily gain the self-confidence of their children than parents that are rebellious or in conflict. They become their children's main soul mate while peer group becomes minor sounding board. Children of homes that are living through peace are more emotionally, mentally and psychologically firm and not likely to exhibit positive attitude towards unrest.

Learning of virtues such as hard work, trust, transparency, honesty and accountability by children, as well as social processes of monitoring and supervision on the part of the parents become easy tasks. Children of such homes seem to develop high self-esteem and are not likely to give in to negative peer pressure. They are most likely instead, to be rigid conformists to family and societal norms who will develop into conformist adults (Ogege & Muoboghare, 2013).

Children are habitually perceptive about the attitudes, behaviours and feelings of their parents and careers. They commonly acknowledge that they, as well as their parents, have an impact on their upbringing. When children understands strong parental attachments of love, spending time together, sympathy, considerate and rewards of pro-social attitude instead of conflicts, bickering, harassments, continuous non-appearance of parents from home, the tendency is for children to imitate more to family and societal norms (Hollist, Lorine & Lornie, 2009).

Children, particularly undergraduates seem to make their parents their replicas. They value and respect their parents' view above those of their peers. Through strong attachment with children, parents get to know who are the associates of their children, those they hang down with, and know their where about. And so, the children grow to value and regard their parents, they would not like to do anything that would upset the parents' feelings or make them cross. Typically, they would rather give in return the love and belief of their parents with the desired conforming behaviour.

Peer pressure extends to all groups and it can be good and bad. A peer group refers to persons that belong to the same age (or about the same age) and/or status. Most students in universities belong to one peer group or the other and it appears that such groups can easily effect each other. There are various pressure groups on campus which are in form of societies or clubs. Universally, the drive of such pressure groups is to represent fellow students in some fashion. The effort to improve and protect the right of each other could be noticeable in

confrontation at any slight vexation. Some students even joined some unregistered associations or groups as a result of peer pressure. Peer groups or associations have their own philosophies, sanctions or rituals into which members are mingled and, accordingly, members (especially new members) who do not meet the terms with any of these may be ostracised (Carlson, 2010).

Peer groups, especially teenage and adolescent peer groups, present to members models of manners. These models are not merely presentations but are actually gifted sometimes and chastised at other times. These groups sometimes do not only have principles that differ from those of the greater society but which also, sometimes, are in antagonism. Yet because members wish to be accepted, they behave like the meaningful others (other members of the in-group). Ogbemor (2012) recognized that human being learns by imitation and noted that in Nigeria youths, through this method, learn the act of crime. According to him, most ferocious crimes in Nigeria, are committed by youths..

It has been perceived that some students give in to peer pressure because they want associates who can combat for their cause and interest at whatever time matter arises, for example, there might be a strong pressure on particular group of students to retaliate the death of another student which can lead to students' unrest. Also, in September 2012, students believed to be cultists in Ekiti State University went on rampage in an attempt to combat the death of one of them and set six vehicles parked in front of the Administrative block on fire and no fewer than fifteen vehicles were badly damaged (Researcher's eyewitness account).

Peer pressure may result in undergraduates progressive or harmful actions. When it results to harmful actions, it implies that it is pressure not to obey the norms of society but to conform and be involved in violent activity. This gives rise to non-conforming or criminally oriented individuals in society. Peer pressure appears to become the strongest impact on undergraduates in terms of prostitution, violence and involvement in unrest in universities, alcohol use, cigarette smoking, drug use and involvement in cultist examination malpractice,.

Despite all the strategies used by university authorities in curbing students' unrest, the menace seems to be on the increase in Southwest, Nigeria. It was for this reason that this study investigated family upbringing and peer pressure and students' attitude to unrest. The study investigated family upbringing and peer pressure as correlates of undergraduates' attitude to unrest in Universities in Southwest, Nigeria. The study specifically examined:

- i. the attitude of undergraduates to unrests in universities;
- ii. the relationship between family upbringing and undergraduates' attitude to unrest; and
- iii. the relationship between peer pressure and undergraduates' attitude to unrest.

Research Question

This research question was raised to guide the study:

1. What is the attitude of undergraduates to unrests in universities in Southwest, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were generated for this study:

1. There is no significant relationship between family upbringing and undergraduates' attitude to unrest.
2. There is no significant relationship between peer pressure and undergraduates' attitude to unrest.

Methodology

The descriptive research design of the survey type was used in this study. The population consisted of all undergraduates from 15 public universities in Southwest, Nigeria. The sample for this study consisted of 1,768 undergraduates selected from six public universities. The sample was selected through multistage sampling procedures.

A questionnaire tagged "Undergraduates' Attitude to Unrest Questionnaire (UAUQ)" designed by the researcher was used to collect data for the study. Section A of the instrument sought for comprehensive bio-data of the respondents while Section B consisted of 10 items which sought for information on family upbringing factor and peer pressure factor. Section C consisted of 10 items which sought information on the attitudes of undergraduates towards unrest in universities. The instrument was prepared using four-point Likert type scale with Strongly Agree (SD) – 4, Agree (A) – 3, Disagree (D) – 2, and Strongly Disagree (SD) – 1 as options. The validity of the instrument was ensured using face and content validity. The items in the Questionnaire were presented to specialists in the fields of Tests, Measurement & Evaluation and Social Studies. Their observations were used to effect the necessary correction on the instrument. The final draft of the instrument was restructured to meet the content validity. The reliability of the instrument was determined through test re-test method. The data collected from the two tests were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Analysis. A co-efficient of 0.74 was obtained from the analysis which was considered statistically high enough to make the instrument reliable.

The data collected from the questionnaires were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The research question was answered using frequency count, percentages, mean and standard deviation. The hypotheses were tested using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the attitude of undergraduates to unrests in universities in Southwest, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of attitude of undergraduates to unrest in South West Nigerian Universities

S / N	ITEMS	N	Mean	Expected Mean	SD	Remark
1	Students prefer physical demonstration than to accept management demand	1768	3.00	2.50	0.91	Accepted
2	Students are always sad during unrest	1768	1.25	2.50	0.45	Rejected
3	Students don't pay much attention to unrest	1768	1.17	2.50	0.49	Rejected
4	Students show interest during unrest	1768	3.21	2.50	0.87	Accepted
5	Students are motivated when they come together to fight a common goal	1768	2.92	2.50	0.95	Accepted
6	Students are not always happy when	1768	2.83	2.50	0.94	Accepted

.	schools are shut down as a result of unrest					
7	Students' unrest is necessary because that is language the Management understands	1768	2.79	2.50	0.87	Accepted
8	Students can only achieve what they want management to do when they make trouble with them	1768	2.87	2.50	1.05	Accepted
9	Students participate actively in any act to fight for their rights	1768	2.71	2.50	1.06	Accepted
10	Students prefer to talk things over with those concerned instead of violence	1768	2.92	2.50	1.04	Accepted
	Total		2.57			

Mean cut off: 2.50

Table 1 revealed the attitude of undergraduates to unrests in universities in Southwest, Nigeria. The table revealed that the respondents have positive attitude to unrest. The respondents have positive attitude to all the items raised which include preferring physical demonstration than to accept management demand, they are always happy during unrest, they pay much attention to unrest and show interest during unrest, they are motivated when they come together to fight a common cause among others. Based on the remark and average total mean of 2.57, students have positive attitude towards unrests in universities in Southwest, Nigeria.

Testing of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between family upbringing and undergraduates' attitude to unrest.

In testing this hypothesis, data on family upbringing were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of UAUQ (item 1 – 5) in the questionnaire. Also, data on undergraduates' attitude toward unrest were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section C of UAUQ (item 1 – 10) in the questionnaire. Both sets of data were compared for statistical significance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 levels. The result is presented in table 2.

Table 2: Relationship between family upbringing and undergraduates' attitude to unrest

Variables	N	r-cal	r-tab	Remark
Family Upbringing	1768	0.705*	0.195	Significant
Attitude to Unrest	1768			

*P<0.05

Table 2 showed r-cal (0.705) is greater than r-table (0.195) at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between family upbringing and undergraduates' attitude to unrest. Hence, family upbringing is positively and highly related to undergraduates' attitude to unrest.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between peer pressure and undergraduates' attitude to unrest.

In testing this hypothesis, data on peer pressure were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of UAUQ (item 6 – 10) in the questionnaire. Also, data on undergraduates' attitude toward unrest were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section C of UAUQ (item 1 – 10) in the questionnaire. The two sets of data were compared for statistical significance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 levels. The result is presented in table 3.

Table 3: Relationship between peer pressure and undergraduates' attitude to unrest

Variables	N	r-cal	r-tab	Remark
Peer Pressure	1768	0.688*	0.195	Significant
Attitude towards Unrest	1768			

*P<0.05

Table 3 showed r-cal (0.688) is greater than r-table (0.195) at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between peer pressure and undergraduates' attitude to unrest. Hence, peer pressure is positively and highly related to undergraduates' attitude to unrest.

Discussion

The findings on undergraduates' attitude to unrest revealed that students prefer physical demonstration than negotiating with concerned authority. Students are always happy during unrest, they pay much attention and show interest in unrest, they participate actively in unrest and also prefer violence than negotiation. This finding supports the submission of David (2013) who concluded from his studies that students have a relatively positive attitude towards unrest as they consider it as very important in pressing home their demands.

The findings of the study revealed that significant relationship existed between family upbringing and undergraduates' attitude to unrest. If a parent acts in a positive or negative way, the child is more likely to follow their parent's positive or negative attitude. They are also more likely to generalize this attitude to the rest of the society. Thus, family upbringing has much influence over the child's attitude to unrest. This finding is in consonance with the findings of Barnes (2006) and Buehler (2006) who found out that family upbringing influence students' attitude to unrest. They further concluded that when the family bond is destabilized through parental conflict, there are advanced levels of the youth expressing their problems on the society which are usually in the form of crisis. Ibrahim (2012) also concluded that factors from the home environment in the upbringing process also affect students' attitude to unrest.

The findings of the study also revealed that there was significant relationship between peer pressure and undergraduates' attitude towards unrest. This finding might be as a result of peer group influence as students are under pressure to conform to peer subculture because the group consists of friends and people that they value highly and depend on for getting along in life. This finding is consistent with the submission of Igbinovia (2003) who submitted that peer pressure is one of the causes of students' unrest in our tertiary institutions.

Conclusion

It was concluded that students are always happy during unrest, they pay much attention and show interest in unrest, they participate actively in unrest and also prefer

violence than negotiation. In addition, family upbringing and peer pressure are related to undergraduates' attitude to unrest.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study.

1. Parents are of central significance in their children's life, so they should adequately give their children proper home training and necessary support that will be needed by the children in the University and throughout life.
2. In order to avoid negative peer pressure, school authorities should establish functional professional counselling units to provide counselling and psychological services to students to reduce behavioural activities that run counter to societal and institutional expectations.

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